

Studies on Dithiocarbamates : Part VIII. Alkaline Hydrolysis of Azorhodanines

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The dependence of the absorption spectra of the title compounds on the nature of the substituents in 40% methanol-buffer systems has been investigated. Correlation of pK_A values with Hammett σ or Taft σ_R parameters indicates the possibility of intramolecular hydrogen-bond in solution phase at least in some cases. The apparent rate constants, k_{ob} in sec^{-1} , derived from kinetic runs over the pH range 7 to 12 at 25° , show a fair linear relationship with Taft σ_R values. The pH -rate profiles, which are virtually independent at $pH \geq 10$, suggest that the rate-determining step involves the formation of an anionic complex. An equation has been developed to explain the observed results.

In anticipation that a combination of $-\text{NCS}$ and $-\text{N}=\text{N}-$ group in a single structural unit would provide a potentially powerful toxophore, a series of azorhodanines (I) have been recently described by us.^{1,2} The list of compounds so far reported from these laboratories include compounds with usual variations at N_3 as well as at C_6 . But the stability data coupled with nature of the breakdown product (s), if possible under simulated condition, are now recognised as tools to seek important leads to the potentiality of a compound.

To this end, systematic investigations have been initiated on a series of azorhodanines derived from 3-benzylrhodanine. Present studies are mainly concerned with investigations on pK_A values of II as well as their kinetic studies over the pH range 7 to 12. In this connection, special attention was directed towards the role of a polar substituent (in azophenyl group) in elucidating the probable course of degradation.

The choice of selecting 3-benzyl derivatives (II) was mainly guided by their ready availability³, but 3-benzylrhodanines are also known³ to provide highly active

1. P. B. Talukdar and S. K. Sengupta, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **44**, 104.
2. P. B. Talukdar and S. K. Sengupta, *Ibid*, in press.
3. F. C. Browns, *Chem. R. v.*, 1961, **61**, 463.

toxicants. It is also interesting to note that there are relatively few investigations⁴ on the hydrolysis of azodyes in comparison to their technical importance.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials : The following buffer solutions were prepared according to Vogel⁵ : pH 5.05 (acetate), 5.80 (acetate), 7.05 (phosphate), 8.10 (borate), 8.90 (borate) and 10.00 (borate).

Besides, dilute solutions of caustic soda, pH 11.70 and 12.00, were also used for studies under strongly alkaline condition. But in all cases, the ionic strength was maintained at 0.1 by added potassium chloride.

The quoted pH values are those of the corresponding aqueous solution. The actual pH of the 40% methanol-buffer medium used in the kinetic studies would probably differ by a small and constant amount.

Acetone-free methanol (BDH) was used in preparing the stock solution of azorhodanines which were available to us from our previous^a studies.

Isobestic points were determined with Hilger Ultrascan (recording) spectrophotometer using 1 c.m. quartz cells. Rate measurements as well as pK_A determinations were carried out with Hilger UVI SPEK spectrophotometer in 1 c.m. matched quartz cells.

Isobestic point and pK_A measurement : The sample solution and the appropriate buffer were first thermostated at 25° and aliquot portions of them were quickly mixed in a volumetric flask. The mixed solution was immediately scanned and all the operations were usually completed within three minutes. The concentration of the dye was always adjusted in such a way that the absorbance values at λ_{max} were around unity. The observed values are recorded in table-I.

TABLE I
Some physical properties of Azorhodanines (II)

No.	R	Isobestic pt. m μ		pK_A (± 0.05)	λ_{max}^{pH9} m μ	$\Delta \lambda_{max}^{pH7\sim 9}$ m μ	Hammett Const (σ) (a)	Taft Const (σ_R) (b)
1	H	455 \pm 2	370 \pm 1	8.10	487	52	0	0
2	<i>p</i> -Me	457 \pm 3	375 \pm 3	7.90	486	46	-0.17	-0.12
3	<i>p</i> -MeO	467 \pm 3	380 \pm 3	7.48	490	39	-0.27	-0.52
4	<i>p</i> -EtO	467 \pm 2	380 \pm 3	7.55	490	36	-0.25	-(0.40)*
5	<i>p</i> -Cl	456 \pm 2	376 \pm 2	7.70	492	59	+0.227	-0.24
6	<i>p</i> -Br	460 \pm 2	378 \pm 2	7.95	492	62	+0.232	-0.22
7	<i>p</i> -I	462 \pm 2	377 \pm 2	8.00	495	65	+0.276	-0.10
8	<i>p</i> -OH	478 \pm 2	378 \pm 2	7.90	492	35	-0.37	-0.62
9	- <i>p</i> CO ₂ H	458 \pm 2	375 \pm 3	7.95	498	68	+0.45	+0.20
10	<i>p</i> -SO ₂ NH ₂	453 \pm 2	369 \pm 2	7.20	502	84	+0.57	—
11	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	473 \pm 2	—	7.25	552	117	+0.778 (1.270)	+0.64
12	<i>m</i> -Cl	450 \pm 2	367 \pm 2	7.65	490	68	+0.373	-0.11
13	<i>m</i> -OH	457 \pm 2	373 \pm 2	7.90	487	52	+0.21	-0.25

(a) Quoted from ref. 12, p. 173. (b) Quoted from ref 9.

(c) Erroneously reported 7.60, *This Journal*, 1967, 44, 350.

(*) $\sigma_R \approx \sigma_p - \sigma_m = -0.40$.

4. H. Zollinger, 'Azo and Diazochemistry,' 1961, Interscience Publishers, New York, p. 29 .

5. A. Vogel, 'A Text book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis', 1959, Longmans, Green & Co., London, p. 869.

The pK_A 's were graphically derived from the best fit of data obtained from the following equation

$$pH = pK_A + \log \frac{A - A_A}{A_B - A}$$

where A , A_A and A_B are the corresponding absorbances in buffer, acid (0.1 M HCl) and alkali (0.1 M NaOH) at a λ max corresponding to that in alkaline medium.

As systematic error is likely to be introduced due to inherent instability of the compounds, pK_A values were calculated with extrapolated zero-time readings. Influence of ionic strength has been ignored in the above calculations.

Kinetic measurements : Data reported in Table-II, were obtained from runs conducted with methanol-buffer mixture containing 40% v/v methanol. The ionic strength of the resultant solutions was 0.06.

The visible band of azorhodanines undergoes profound change under alkaline condition. Hence, all rate studies were conducted at 25° by following the disappearance of colour at λ max appropriate to buffer pH.* Runs were usually followed until the solutions were practically colourless. Details of the measurements have been described previously⁶ and the measured temperature was constant within $\pm 0.2^\circ$.

Rate constants were calculated from the integrated first order equation and plots of log absorbance vs. time were invariably excellent straight lines. The rate constants for the overall reactions were all accurate to $\pm 3\%$ or better by agreement between duplicate experiments.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Absorption spectra and Isobestic points : The visible band, in comparison to any other band in the UV region, suffers a steady and fairly rapid loss of intensity with time ; at the same time, there was a bathochromic shift in λ max with maximum displacement occurring around pH 9. Indeed, further increase in pH of the medium had no significant effect on the position of λ max. As a result, two isobestic points could be discerned in the visible region for all cases except in the case of p -NO₂ compound (Table-I). But the observed spread, although small (± 2 to 3 $m\mu$), deserve some comments. This phenomenon may be attributed to partial decomposition during the experimental work or due to difference in solvation of the anion at various pH. Thus, similar lack of convergence was detected⁷ in the case of

* The observed rate would indicate the rate of loss of azo-structure in II leading to the formation of a transition state which disintegrates at a faster rate to yield decomposition products. Hence, k_{ob} would be a measure of the overall hydrolytic decomposition of the azo-compounds,

6. P. B. Talukdar and S. Banerjee, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, 44, 1060.

7. R. Kuhn and F. Bar, *Ann.*, 1935, 516, 143 and ref. 4, p. 324.

4-phenylazo-1-naphthol and this was ascribed to the great difference in solvating power of the media used.

Fig. 1. Plots of shift in λ_{\max} between pH 7 & 9 against Hammett σ constants.

In this connection it is highly significant to note the existence of a linear relationship (Fig. 1) between Hammett's constant and the difference in λ_{\max} between pH 7 & 9 ($\Delta \lambda_{\max}^{\text{pH } 7 \sim 9}$, Table-I). It may be construed as an indication of *nobreak* in the mechanism of transmission of the electronic effects of the substituents. Further, the compounds are almost completely ionised between pH 9 and 10.

At any rate, the above statements do not explain the mode of transmission of the electronic effects in the light of recent work by Dewar¹⁰ on field effects. But it is worthwhile to point out that we are mainly dealing with *p*-substituents with negative charge, by and large, dispersed on the five membered ring, at least in alkaline medium. Hence, we feel that polarisation of the intervening conjugated system is the principal mode of operation. Presumably, *trans* orientation is the preferred system (III) in order to account for the observed results. This is in agreement with our previous findings⁸; and the observations of Eian and Kingsbury¹¹

8. (a) H. H. Jaffe, *Chem. Rev.*, 1953, 53, 191.

(b) P. R. Wells, *Chem. Rev.*, 1963, 63, 171.

9. (a) R. W. Taft in *Steric Effects in Organic Chemistry*, Ed. by M. S. Newman, 1956, Chap. 13, John Wiley & Sons, New York.

(b) R. W. Taft, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1960, 64, 1805.

10. M. J. S. Dewar and P. J. Grisdale, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 84, 3548.

11. G. L. Eian and C. A. Kingsbury, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1967, 32, 1862.

that ϵ is highly sensitive to ring co-planarity in a resonating system is also relevant in this context.

pK_A values : The acidities of azorhodanines are undoubtedly associated with-M character of the azophenyl residue ($\sigma = +0.64$)⁸ at C₅. Consequently, the observed pK_A values are anticipated to reflect the change in-M character due to the introduction of substituent in the phenyl-ring. To this end, results were indeed surprising to the extent that the attempted free energy relationship between pK_A vs. Hammett σ or Taft σ_R ⁹ always produced a break at about $\sigma = 0$, (Fig-2). This is difficult to understand in terms of the anion (A) generated at the initial stage or any other mesomeric form with the negative charge dispersed on the five-membered ring (B & C).

Fig. 2. Plots of pK_A against substituent constants (σ or σ_R)

Now, it is already recognised¹² that a break in the free energy relationship suggest a change either in the mechanism, or in the rate-limiting step in a sequence of reactions. In this context, examination of the structural features of the anion

becomes a pertinent issue. As shown above, a number of limiting structures could be drawn up for the anion generated from II. Evidently, the limiting structure D is important for some of the compounds under the experimental conditions in order to account for the observed sequence of pK_A values. Thus, in the normal course of events with participation of conjugating $-N=N-$ bond in the transmission of electronic effects, *p*-methoxy- or ethoxy derivatives should have higher pK_A values than those of *p*-halogenated derivatives; but the reverse trend is quite apparent. (Table-I).

Hence, we believe that the anion from II could be more correctly represented by structure E and the relative importance of any particular limiting structure is dictated by the prevailing conditions. As a corollary, the existence of H-bonded structure (IV) becomes a possibility, at least in the solution phase; and the diazo derivatives¹³ of 2-pyrazolin-5-one, for instance, is a relevant case in point.

Kinetic Study :

pH dependence : The apparent first order rate constants for alkaline hydrolysis of azorhodanines are summarised in Table-II. But in order to comprehend the

TABLE II

The observed rate constants, $10^4 k_{ob}$ in sec^{-1} , in 40% methanol buffer at various pH.

No.	R	7.05	8.10	8.90	10.00	11.70	12.00
1	H	*	1.1514	1.2340	1.3130	1.4680	1.4680
2	<i>p</i> -Me	*	*	0.7196	0.8397	0.8722	0.8857
3	<i>p</i> -MeO	0.1535	0.2952	0.3030	0.4040	0.3838	0.3998
4	<i>p</i> -EtO	*	0.3656	0.3656	0.3937	0.4260	0.4264
5	<i>p</i> -Cl	*	0.9139	0.9139	0.9956	1.0230	1.0230
6	<i>p</i> -Br	0.4039	1.0100	1.0660	1.0970	1.1515	1.1515
7	<i>p</i> -I	0.5905	1.0470	1.0960	1.1990	1.2790	1.2790
8	<i>p</i> -OH	0.2399	1.7450	3.3260	14.4000	17.4500	18.4200
9	<i>p</i> -CO ₂ H	0.2565	1.6450	1.8060	2.1690	2.3030	2.3030
10	<i>p</i> -SO ₂ NH ₂	0.9594	2.3750	2.4420	2.4420	2.0460	1.9190
11	<i>p</i> -NO ₂	1.4400	2.0190	2.3990	2.3990	3.2310	4.9670
12	<i>m</i> -OH	0.1949	1.0230	1.1810	1.3160	1.4920	1.5630
13	<i>m</i> -Cl	*	1.1990	1.3440	1.3720	1.6240	1.6240

* Interference due to precipitation.

13. H. Yasuda and H. Midorikawa, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1966, **31**, 1722 see also ref.1 and D. L. Ross and E. Reissner, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1966, **31**, 2571.

significance of rate data, familiarity with pH -rate profiles are of utmost importance. To this end, such profiles of two typical members bearing substituents of opposite polar character are reproduced in Fig. 3. This generality is also found in the case of the p -hydroxy compound (no. 8, table-II), but a separate discussion is necessary for its significantly different rate of reaction, specially at a higher pH .

Fig. 3. Dependence of $\log K_{obs}$ against pH .

Principal conclusions derived from such profiles are as follows. Rate promotion is slow at the initial stages and is partially dependent on the alkali concentration. But rates are practically pH independent at $pH \geq 10$. This kind of pH -independent behaviour has been previously observed by us in the case of 1 : 3-disubstituted 1 : 3 : 5-tetrahydrothiadiazine-2-thiones⁶ as well as by others in cases of Schiff's bases¹⁴, 2-methyloxazoline¹⁵ and so on. In relation to our present studies, the observed data, therefore, strongly suggest decomposition of an activated complex formed through a rate-determining step where the hydroxide ion is likely to participate either as a nucleophile to the substrate or its role may be restricted to liberating the anion from the substrate.

In the light of the above comments, the decomposition of the azorhodanines (SH) could be formulated in terms of the following equation :

14. R. K. Chaturvedi and E. H. Cordes, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **89**, 1231.

15. R. Greenhalgh, R. M. Heggie and M. A. Weinberger, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1963, **41**, 1662.

At any state, the total concentration of the substrate, $[SH]_T$, may be expressed as,

$$[SH]_T = [SH] + [S^-]$$

Using equations (1) and (2),

$$[SH]_T = [SH] \left[1 + \frac{K_1}{[H_3O^+]} + K_2 [OH^-] \right] \quad \dots \quad (5)$$

If the rates are dependent on both $[SH]$ and $[S^-]$, then it could be readily shown from equations (3), (4) and (5), that

$$K_{ob} [SH] \left[1 + \frac{K_1}{[H_3O^+]} + K_2 [OH^-] \right] = k_1 [SH] [OH^-] + k_2 [S^-] [H_2O]$$

$$\text{or, } k_{ob} = \frac{k_1 + k_2 \left(\frac{K_1}{K_w} + K_2 \right)}{1/[OH^-] + \frac{K_1}{K_w} + K_2} \quad \dots \quad (6)$$

Where K_w is the ionisation constant of water and the remaining parameters are defined by eq. 1-4.

The observed rate constants thus show dependence on the hydroxide ion concentration at a lower pH . Evidently, $1/[OH^-]$ is very small and may be neglected at a higher pH . Hence partial dependence at a lower pH independent behaviour at a higher pH could be satisfactorily explained by eq. (6).

Now, from the known values of pK_A and K_w , K_1 and K_2 could be determined; for instance, $K_1 \approx 10^{-9}$ and $K_2 \approx 10^7$ for the p -nitro compound. Again, from the known concentration of the substrate ($C \approx 3 \times 10^{-5}$ mole/l), it may be shown that at $pH \geq 10$, $[SH] \leq 1/30 [S^-]$. Therefore, it could be argued that the reaction mainly proceeds through eq. (4). Under this limiting condition, the estimated value for $k_2 \approx 10^{-3.5}$ mole $^{-1}$ sec $^{-1}$, hence the total reaction could be reasonably explained only with small numerical values for k_1 . Since pK_A values for the whole series vary within a small range (table-I), similar behaviour of the other members are reasonably within expectation.

Substituent Effects; Although gross pattern of the pH -rate profile is identical in all cases the relative ratio of rates, $k_{ob}(pH 10.0)/k_{ob}(pH 7.05)$, is approximately 60 for the p -hydroxy derivative, whereas this ratio varies from 2 to 6 for other members. Apparently, the anion decomposes (eq.4) at faster rate in this instance. This implies reduced steric requirement at the transition state. Hence the site of solvation resulting from ease of charge migration (to phenolic OH group) must be the cause of this singularly different behaviour. This argument is supported by the

observed trend of the *m*-hydroxy compound. But paucity of data does not allow us to commit anything more at this stage. (fig. 4)

Fig. 4. Taft σ_R plot for the alkaline hydrolysis of azorhodanines at 25°.

The observed rate constants ($\log k_{ob}$) failed to correlate the usual Hammett σ values over the entire pH range. The trend suggests a break at about $\sigma=0$, with the electron donating groups forming a well-knit group by themselves. More precisely, a set of lines with opposing slopes could be visualized (fig. 4). In terms of extrathermodynamic relationship, a change^{12, 14} in the interaction mechanism is involved in the given instances. As most Hammett values deal with combined inductive and resonance interaction, the lack of dependence of the observed rate constants on σ values could be reasonably attributed to overriding influence of resonance interaction of the substituents under the experimental condition.

Validity of this argument is justified with a fairly improved fit of data with Taft resonance parameter (σ_R) (fig. 4).

TABLE III

Reaction constants (ρ), correlation coefficients (r) and std. deviations for the hydrolysis of azorhodanines* at various pH and at 25°.

pH	ρ	r	s	No. of Comps.
12.0	0.84	0.93	0.11	10
11.7	0.69	0.88	0.12	10
10.0	0.63	0.82	0.12	10
8.9	0.64	0.82	0.15	10
8.1	0.62	0.77	0.18	9

* *p*-hydroxy compound is excluded.

While the value of ρ did not alter materially between pH 8.1 and 11.7 increasing dispersion could be discerned from poorer correlation coefficients (r) with lowering of

pH. This is understandable in terms of known pK_A values as discussed earlier. But the positive value of ρ is consistent with modest acceleration of rate with electron demanding substituents and strongly suggests^{8,18} the anionic character of the species involved in the rate-determining step. Further, the better fit with exalted resonance value for the *p*-nitro group conform to this view. For lack of any suitable model, the derived value of ρ may be compared with that obtained in the alkaline hydrolysis of *trans*-ethyl cinnamates ($\rho=1.31$)¹⁶. As the value of ρ did not change substantially with change in polarity¹⁷ of the medium, somewhat lower value of ρ may be ascribed to the dispersion (resonance effect) of the charge in the anionic species as observed by Hegarty and Scott¹⁸ in the formation of formazans.

On the basis of the above data, it is suggested that alkaline decomposition of azorhodanines is a multistep process. Presumably, either II or its anion participates in a rate-determining step in the formation of an activated complex prior to its decomposition. Presence of alkali, by and large, is beneficial to the extent that it provides a stronger nucleophile in generating the anionic species. But additional information is required in order to elucidate the degradative pathway and this would be taken up in a subsequent communication.

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17. D. J. Pasto, K. Groves and M. P. Serve, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1967, 32, 774.
18. A. F. Hegarty and F. L. Scott., *J. Org. Chem.*, 1967, 32, 1957.